

IMPROVING THE SYSTEM AND CONTENT OF SELECTION OF CHILDREN FOR THE SPORT OF BELT WRESTLING

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Аннотация: целью статьи является совершенствование системы отбора детей для занятия борьбой на поясах с помощью анкетирования. В статье представлены различные формы вопросов, дана статистика по данным анкетирования; представлен анализ научно-методической литературы, актуальность и цель данной тематики, а также выводы и рекомендации для получения общего представления о борьбе на поясах.

Ключевые слова: поясная борьба, анкета, респондент, спорт, отбор, система, совершенствование, подготовка, умение

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ И СОДЕРЖАНИЯ ОТБОРА ДЕТЕЙ ДЛ Я ЗАНЯТИЙ БОРЬБОЙ НА ПОЯСАХ

Abstract: The purpose of the article is to improve the system of selecting children for belt wrestling by using questionnaires. The article presents various forms of questions, provides statistics on the survey data, analyzes the scientific and methodological literature, the relevance and purpose of this topic, as well as conclusions and recommendations in order to get a detailed view of belt wrestling.

Keywords: belt wrestling, questionnaire, respondent, sport, selection, system, improvement, training, skill.

INTRODUCTION

Today in our country special attention is paid to the development of our national types of wrestling. 122 of March 4, 2020. 4 on measures to further improve the system of selection of athletes for national teams in sports and the results of the study of this article to some extent serve to implement the tasks set out in other regulations in this area. Development of recommendations for the increasing and implementation of methods for improving the system and content of selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling.

T. Usmonxo'jaev, R. Salamov, F. Kerimov, Sh. Xonkeldiev, A. Abdullaev, R. Xalmuxamedov, V. Shin G. Abdurasulova, S.Tajibaev, Sh. Mirzakulov. N. Azizov, J. Nurshin, and others conducted research and developed new information and recommendations that justify the system of selection in textbooks, manuals, articles and theses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on the analysis of the above scientific literature, a survey was conducted to study the theoretical and practical state of improving the system and content of selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling and to identify problems in the selection.

1-graph Problem selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling. (%)

№	Questions	Answer %							
		1-respond	%	2-respond	%	3-respond	%	4-respond	%
1	Liked the training sessions for the	Love	77	Like	15	Uncertain	8	Do not like	0

	primary training groups in children								
2	assessing the process of selection and referral of children to sports in the sports school where they work	Excellent	15	good	19	unsatisfactory	27	Bad	39
3	what age do you think it is acceptable to admit children to the sport of belt wrestling.	From 9	7	From 10	13	From 11	41	From 12	39
4	you select talented children for the sport of belt wrestling	Yes	16	No	23	According to recommendation of a doctor	37	Do not know the method	25
5	what do you look for when selecting children for belt wrestling	Anthropometric indicators	31	Interests of the child	25	Physical abilities.	27	anthropometric indicators and physical abilities	17
6	Where you get information on the selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling	From books	10	From articles	7	From professional experiences	53	From websites	30
7	How many of the students in primary preparation phase will stop wrestling	In the half of the first academic year	31	In the first year	40,6	In the second year	39,8	In the third year	19,8
8	What do you think are the reasons why school children stop participating in sports school in the initial preparation stage?	From the mistake in the selection process	66	Not to have coaching experiences	14	difficulty of developing skills in sports	12	Inability to communicate with children	8

The results of the survey showed that (100%), of the respondents liked the training sessions for the primary training groups in children and youth sports school, the respondents (77 %) are loved, (15 %) just liked, (8 %) undecided. However, when asked how they assess the process of selection and referral of children to sports in the sports school where they work, the respondents (27 %) are unsatisfactory, (19 %) good, (15 %) excellent, (39 %) bad. In the next questionnaire, when asked at what age do you think it is acceptable to admit children to the sport of belt wrestling, according to the respondents, they are 11 years old (41%), 12 years old (39%) and 10 years old (13%), even believe that the admission of children from the age of 9 (7%), to belt wrestling training is highly effective. Responses selected by the respondents corresponded to the opinion of 41-39% "Perceptual phases of development of motion function in school-age children, according to A. A. Gujalovsky," [3] also correspond to the age ". The majority of respondents are (16 %), selected children for belt wrestling and admit them to primary training groups. (23%) of respondents do not admit selection, (37 %) maybe they will accept a healthy child who has undergone a medical examination and (25 %) do not know the method. For primary education groups, the question of what to look for when selecting children for belt wrestling was answered by anthropometric indicators (31 %), while respondents (25 %) indicated that they pay attention to the interests of the child, (27 %) focus on the child's physical abilities, (17 %) respondents are anthropometric indicators and child's physical abilities. We can see opinions of respondents (34%), corresponds to research scientist Guba V.P scientifically based research. He noted that children's physical development was assessed by a number of external characteristics: height, weight, body proportions, spine, chest, pelvis, and leg shape and foot size. [4] According to the survey (34%) of respondents believe that the child's interest (34%) should look at the physical abilities, while the scientific and methodological literature. Respondents answered the next question as following. To the question where they get information on the selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling they answered that (10 %) from books, (7 %) from articles, (53 %) from their professional experience, (30 %) from websites. The next question, about how many of the students in the primary preparation phase will stop wrestling, was answered as following: in the half of the first academic year (31 %), in the first academic year (40,6%), in the second academic year (39,8%), in the third academic year (19,8%). The following question will help us understand how important it is to qualify and refer children to sports. To the question "What do you think are the reasons why school children stop participating in sports school in the initial preparation stage ?" respondents (66%) rated the selection process as a mistake, (14%) said they did not have coaching experience, (12%) respondents chose the answer to the difficulty of developing skills in sports, respondents (8%) chose the answer to the inability to communicate with children .

1-pictura. In our closed test, to the question "What methodological assistance do you need to improve the quality of training and maintain the contingent of trainees, (57%) respondents

answered that they need for methodological recommendations and guidelines for selection and referral. (43%) of respondents wrote that there is a need for guidelines for movement games with special age-appropriate, gender-specific wrestling elements for children aged 11-12 years [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this questionnaire, respondents were introduced to action games with 55 individual wrestling elements and then presented with the following questionnaire [2]. You recommend using belt wrestling, which is close to the sport, and children in qualifying for this sport (indicate the levels in numbers 1,2,3,4,5,). Analysis of respondents' responses showed that belt wrestling was close to the sport and that level 1 matches (28%) used for qualifying were selected as “Pull the handkerchief”, “Take out of a circle” “Struggle against capture”, 2 matches (24%) “Pushing out of the circke”, “Touching the legs” level 3 (19%).) “Fight of Roosters”, Level 4 (16%) “Take possession of a ball”, Level 5 (13%) “Pull faster” and “Own the Ball” were selected by level.

Which sport do you suggest for the sports that are close to belt wrestling and you suggest children in selection to use (the numbers are showed in percents (1,2,3,4,5,).

2-pictura. Respondents believe that the above games are not only close to the sport, but also play an important role in the selection and directing of children to the sport of belt wrestling.

According to their answers to the question ‘Which of the following general fitness tests do you recommend to be the most important in the selection of 11-12 year olds for belt wrestling (indicate the number of levels 1,2,3,4,5,)’.

3-pictura. Respondents (49 %) fell for the 1st level test wrestlers, climbed the rope (in any way) (21 %), 2nd level test wrestlers to determine the quality of strength, jumped on the spot, (12%) 3rd level test run 30 meters, (10%) Walking with arms crossed while hanging on a Level 4 test bar, (8%) Jumping on a Level 5 test rope, and cross-country 400 meters respondents gave the

above answers in determining children's physical qualities in qualifying for belt wrestling. It is clear from the above answers that the process of qualifying children for the sport of belt wrestling shows the need to develop a system based on certain criteria.

CONCLUSION

Experts should pay attention to the following criteria when selecting the sport of belt wrestling using the results of the survey, as well as the analysis of scientific and methodological literature:

- age and gender of students, the presence of skills related to the sport of wrestling;
- individual abilities of students, general physical development related to the sport of wrestling;
- the suitability of the type of wrestling and the character and temperament of the student;
- The composition of the skills related to the sport of wrestling, and to what extent it is developed
- in determining the abilities of children using movement games with elements of single combat;

The study of the process of selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling is a topical area and requires further research. The selection of children for the sport of belt wrestling has been proposed by a number of experts to be considered as a continuous process that covers all the main stages of long-term training of athletes. Therefore, in the first stage, it should be characterized by the direction of the sport, in the process of identifying, assessing and forecasting the abilities of this athlete, and in the selection process we should direct children to this sport, which corresponds to the sport of belt wrestling.

Used literature

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